

The 'Context Language' System.

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ABSTRACT. This development presents a systems language[1] in which we'll name 'Nectar' (CL). We propose a method of programming language design in which Execution is separated from Data, alongside trait rules.

1 APPROACH

We represent the CL execution flow as an execution context as a way to mathematically present the following:

$$CL(C) := \frac{d \text{Prog}(\lambda C)}{dC} \quad (1)$$

Such that an execution context (denoted as C) is a program currently running with rules (denoted as Trait(C)) and domains. We derive the program by its context in this formula, as we depend on C, the C variable must be valid and computable in a domain D.

2 THEORY

The syntax of a Context Language may consist of traits, and implementations. The traits can be expressed as defined in Nectar. One way to represent it mathematically is:

$$\text{Trait}(C) := \text{Rules}(C) \in C \quad (2)$$

Traits and such must be valid in C & $\Theta(C)$. Here's an example of a Nectar program calling a 'get' method:

```
1 trait data {
2   let get();
3 }
4
5 impl data : trait data {
6   let get(let self) {
7
8   }
9 }
10
11 const main() {
12   let s := data{};
13   s.get();
14   return 0;
15 }
```

3 REFERENCES

[1] Keays, Roger, and Andry Rakotonirainy. "Context-Oriented Programming." Proceedings of the 3rd ACM International Workshop on Data Engineering for Wireless and Mobile Access [San Diego CA USA], 2003, pp. 9–16. DOI.org (Crossref), <https://doi.org/10.1145/940923.940926>.